

THE EFFECT OF UREA CREATININE ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF TUBULOINTERSTITIAL FIBROSIS IN CHRONIC GLOMERULONEPHRITIS.

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ABSTRACT

Chronic glomerulonephritis (CGN) is one of the main causes of chronic kidney disease and end-stage renal failure. One of the leading morphological manifestations of CGN progression is tubulointerstitial fibrosis (TIF), the formation of which is closely associated with impaired excretory function of the nephrons. Elevated blood urea and creatinine levels reflect a decrease in glomerular filtration rate and the degree of renal parenchymal damage. Research objective. To evaluate the relationship between changes in urea and creatinine levels and the development of tubulointerstitial fibrosis in patients with chronic glomerulonephritis.

Relevance. Chronic glomerulonephritis (CGN) is one of the main causes of chronic kidney disease and end-stage renal failure. One of the leading morphological manifestations of CGN progression is tubulointerstitial fibrosis (TIF), the formation of which is closely associated with impaired excretory function of the nephrons. Elevated blood urea and creatinine levels reflect a decrease in glomerular filtration rate and the degree of renal parenchymal damage.

Research objective. To evaluate the relationship between changes in urea and creatinine levels and the development of tubulointerstitial fibrosis in patients with chronic glomerulonephritis.

Main content. Increased urea and creatinine concentrations in patients with CGN reflect not only a decrease in renal filtration capacity, but also the activation of pathogenetic mechanisms that contribute to fibrosis. Nitrogenous metabolites induce oxidative stress and an inflammatory response involving cytokines IL-1 β , TNF- α , and TGF- β 1. Under their influence, fibroblasts are activated and the synthesis of extracellular matrix components, in particular collagen types I and III, is enhanced. Uraemic intoxication also contributes to epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), leading to the accumulation of myofibroblasts and the progression of interstitial fibrosis.

Conclusions. Changes in urea and creatinine levels are not only markers of decreased glomerular filtration, but also reflect the activity of fibrogenesis processes in renal tissue. Monitoring these indicators in patients with chronic glomerulonephritis is of important diagnostic and prognostic significance for the early detection and slowing of the development of tubulointerstitial fibrosis.

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